

Title:

Piano Terra, Piano Nobile
A Baroque reasoning in Portuguese New Vernacular

Pedro Duarte Bento¹

¹Architect-Researcher, PhD in Architecture (Field of Theory and Practice of Project), FAUL-Lisboa
Email: pedroduarteporto@gmail.com | www.pedroduarteporto.com

Abstract

During the early Renaissance, a typological shift in spatial hierarchy became evident throughout the *palazzi* of some Italian cities. Whereas the ground floor had previously accommodated main social functions, a new approach emerged: the *piano nobile*—an intentional positioning of the most important program of the building above street level, creating a “noble floor.” This floor housed formal reception rooms and master quarters, providing an opportunity for operative distinction. The custom of elevating the principal floor had already been observed in medieval times, driven by practical concerns such as safety, flood and damp prevention, and the avoidance of street noise and smells. However, during this period of economic growth, the concept evolved. What began as a functional necessity gradually transformed into a symbolic one. As illustrated much later in Nolli’s 18th-century map of Rome, the ground floor could be perceived as part of the public domain. An aspiring exclusivity had to find its place above the people, and the *piano nobile* was the response. As Pevsner suggests, it was intended to display power and provide the wealthy with a superior realm, distinct from—and separated by—the commoners below. This deliberated architectural reasoning would solidify over the next two centuries, reaching its theatrical grandeur during the Baroque.

Stripped of any scholarly bias, this text will draw a parallel between the well-documented historical typology and another—ostensibly less erudite and more prosaic, but perhaps equally relevant in terms of cultural identity. From the 1960s onwards, Portugal witnessed the emergence of novel forms of single-family houses, driven by acculturation and technological advance. Modern, standardized industrial

products and construction techniques became available to rural communities, replacing local materials and the generational building knowledge once so characteristic of each region. Some of these most recognizable types were crystallized in the infamous emigrant-house and the clandestine-house, processes in which architects didn't participate. They formed what Nuno Portas referred to as the *New Vernacular* in the Portuguese context. More recent types have been identified and characterized, namely the polygenic *Generic House*, visible throughout the entirety of the continental territory, detached from regional affiliations and defined by a specific and repeated spatial organization.

Like the Italian *palazzi*, these houses evolved from a rusticated ground floor to a more representational upper level. Many precedent types within the original “old” vernacular featured a space at the ground level known as *loja*. This space served as storage for agricultural tools, crops, and even shelter for livestock such as sheep or goats. In the typological evolution that mirrored the socio-cultural shift from rural to post-rural, the differentiation between the two levels became more pronounced. The rustic *piano terra* remained a functional area —now for garage, family daily room, or prep kitchen—, while the upper floor gained symbolic importance. Exterior staircases and long balconies often adorned the buildings, signaling a shift in both form and function. Modernity reached these communities, bringing with it a sense of social projection and financial achievement. Whether consciously or not, they created their own *piano nobile* to express it.

Keywords: *Typology; Piano Terra & Piano Nobile; Portuguese New Vernacular;*

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20797419

Piano Terra, Piano Nobile
Portuguese New Vernacular, *Casa Genérica* type
Campina (Faro)
Pedro Duarte Bento, 2024